

A compact 100-GHz omnidirectional monopole probe dielectric resonator antenna enabled by micromachined silicon coaxial cavity

Kalliopi Spanidou, Daniel Headland, and Guillermo Carpintero
Optoelectronics and Laser Technology Group, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid,
28911 Madrid, Spain

ABSTRACT

Antenna miniaturization poses a significant challenge at high frequencies, as we must balance performance against physical viability. Here, we present the realization of a coaxial-W1-fed dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) operating above 100 GHz. The dielectric cavity is fabricated from intrinsic silicon using micromachining. Given its simple design and high-precision manufacture, the proposed DRA simplifies assembly by leveraging a precise alignment concept for realizing a compact probe antenna. At the resonance frequency of 107 GHz, we demonstrate insertion loss of -30 dB and matching bandwidth of 4 GHz. Near-field scanning measurements are also performed to confirm that this probe can be used as a cost-effective mm-wave compact antenna test range. With its omnidirectional radiation and compact structure, this DRA holds the potential as a probe antenna to test and evaluate future 6G communications systems.

Keywords: Semiconductors, Coaxial resonators, Silicon, Dielectric resonators, Probe antennas, Micromachining

1. INTRODUCTION

There is growing interest in frequencies in the vicinity of 100 GHz due to the continual evolution of wireless communications up to the terahertz range. Within this frequency range, systems can support greater spectral bandwidth for high-speed data transmission that will be essential to establish future 6G networks. However, the development of technology to exploit this range has been hampered by the lack of viable compact, inexpensive, and general-purpose probe antennas. Omnidirectional probes are beneficial due to their spatial flexibility and multipath characterization capabilities such as debugging in cases of signal leakage, evaluating propagation of MIMO systems, and measuring the complex aperture distribution of high-gain antennas and arrays [1]. Phased arrays in particular can benefit from this technique, as the radiating phase of each individual element can be evaluated, and hence calibrated. Consequently, they are valuable tools in the development and testing of 6G communication systems. However, despite these advantages, here are certain fundamental challenges that are associated with the small physical scale of millimeter-wave (mm-Wave) devices above 100 GHz, and in particular the realization of viable compact and electrically-small antennas. As dimensions decrease, the complexity of fabrication and assembly increases. Therefore, there is a need for assembly-aware designs that mitigate any misalignment between the radiator and feeding structure, as this can significantly impact on the performance of the antenna [2].

In the mm-Wave and terahertz ranges, dielectric resonator antennas (DRA) are attractive for their inherently low-loss, as the mode of resonance utilizes displacement-current rather than conduction current resulting in high radiation efficiency compared to metals, which become increasingly lossy at high frequencies [3]. Conventional DRAs combine metal feeds with dielectric radiators composed of ceramics or polymers, allowing great design flexibility at mm-Wave frequencies [2]. The feeding mechanism can also be exploited as an additional degree of design freedom, with coaxial waveguide-fed DRAs being among the first reported by simply extending the inner conductor of the guide into the volume of the dielectric [4], [5], [6], [7]. By adopting new feeding structures, altering the feed position, or by reshaping and stacking DRAs the overall performance of the antenna can be tailored for diverse applications [8], [9]. Various DRA examples exist in literature using a monopole feed along with complicated DR structures to realize transceiver antennas offering omnidirectional radiation [10], [11], [12] and broad bandwidth. Taking advantage of this great design freedom has been key to meeting the market's growing demands, since physical size, material properties, and impedance bandwidth are highly correlated [13].

In the context of future integrated communication systems, miniaturization of antennas becomes a decisive factor for viability at higher-frequencies. Although the aforementioned complicated resonator structures showcase a number of

attractive properties, their structural complexity represents a major obstacle towards higher-frequency operation. Most integrated on-chip antennas have achieved high radiation efficiency using planar feeds, including half-mode substrate waveguides [14] and coplanar waveguides [15] with additional integrated cavity-backed patches to reach 340 GHz [16]. In these designs, tolerance analysis was required due to alignment issues and manufacturing challenges [15]. This leads us to the conclusion that operation above 100 GHz demands simpler designs to allow for high precision and low-cost manufacture of miniaturized structures, pushing beyond the current limits of fabrication and assembly.

Micromachining of intrinsic silicon appears to play a pivotal role in advancing antenna structures that rely on low-loss dielectrics with precise micro-scale features. This fabrication approach has facilitated the integration of antennas with electronic and photonic circuits for frequencies from 60 to 340 GHz [17], [18], [19]. All these DRAs are based on high-resistivity silicon, showcasing the remarkable performance of this material at high frequencies. Owing to its relatively high electrical permittivity, silicon can be used as an efficient DRA allowing the realization of compact resonant cavity structures [20], [21]. Moving towards photonics applications, a compact DRA integrated with its waveguide feed in an all-dielectric platform achieved end-fire radiation at 320 GHz. Although the all-dielectric integration eliminates any assembly challenges and the DRA is amendable to broadside radiation, its antenna pattern is too directional to serve as a probe antenna [22].

In this work, we propose the simplest assembly for realizing a compact omnidirectional monopole probe antenna operating above 100 GHz. To this end, we employ the simplest assembly approach available; the original coaxial waveguide-fed concept presented by Long et. al. [4]. A W1-103F monopole, compatible with the W1 coaxial standard with 1-mm connection test ports [23], is introduced into a micromachined intrinsic-silicon cavity. Thus, the precise manual alignment makes our DRA a cost-effective antenna solution. Owing to rotational symmetry, omnidirectional radiation patterns are produced by this compact DRA. We experimentally show that insertion loss is improved, achieving $S_{11} < -30$ dB at 106.5 GHz serving as a matching cavity for the realization of coaxial-W1-fed DRA. Interlocking structures allow precise alignment by hand, highlighting its superiority in simplicity, ease of assembly compared to the aforementioned antennas. Such a DRA can therefore be used to assess the overall reliability and connectivity of 6G antenna systems.

2. ANTENNA DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

An intrinsic silicon cylindrical DR is coupled to a W1 coaxial feed that is inserted into a hole in the center, as illustrated in Figs. 1 (a) and (b). The designed DR structure is fabricated by Deep Reactive-Ion Etching (DRIE), also known as micromachining, which is a cost-effective and scalable process to create high-resistivity silicon microstructures with ultra-high precision and highly vertical sidewalls [21]. The cylindrical cavity has an inner radius of 75 μm , corresponding to the 65- μm radius of the probe feed optimized for resonance in the $\text{TM}_{01\delta}$ mode at 106.5 GHz. By minimizing the empty space between the probe and the DR, coupling is enhanced since resonance and ϵ_r are not affected by the presence of an air-gap [15]. In this way, the coaxial gold connector is introduced into the DR through a hole at the center thus, providing high coupling efficiency to the DR's mode of resonance.

Fig. 1. An illustration of (a) 3-dimensional and (b) cross-sectional view of the DRA with the coaxial feed using the W1-103F monopole probe. Simulated E- and H-field distributions of the proposed DRA resonating at 106.5 GHz, with the dominance of the $\text{TM}_{01\delta}$ mode observed in (c) x-y plane, $z=0$ and (d) y-z plane, observed at $z = 300$ μm from the CST Microwave Studio.

Full-wave simulations are employed to investigate the antenna structure. The cylindrical DRA is centrally excited by the W1 monopole probe via a 50 Ω coaxial waveguide, and the resulting pattern of resonance in the cavity is inspected. As shown in Figs. 1 (c) and (d), the appearance of the rotationally-symmetrical transverse magnetic $TM_{01\delta}$ mode mirrors the concentric nature of the structure itself [6]. In this mode, the DRA's radiation pattern is expected to be closely related to that of an electric dipole oriented along the z-axis. The $TM_{01\delta}$ resonant mode is classified as a confined mode since the magnetic field vanishes outside the resonator [24].

3. ANTENNA PERFORMANCE

To verify the matching performance of the proposed DRA, an Anritsu MS4647B Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) equipped with 3743A mm-Wave extension heads was used to measure the reflection coefficient $|S_{11}|$. Fig. 2 (a) depicts a photo of the proposed DRA probe during measurements. Fig. 2 (b) shows the measured and simulated return loss of the cylindrical DRA in comparison with the response of the W1 monopole for the 70-110 GHz band. It is evident that the cylindrical DR with radius of $R = 710 \mu\text{m}$ has greatly improved the antenna matching at 107 GHz very close to the simulated frequency, resonance. The measured reflection coefficient $|S_{11}|$ of the $TM_{01\delta}$ mode reaches -30 dB at the resonance frequency, as intended. Impedance bandwidth was measured at 4 GHz (below -10 dB), which is less than the simulated bandwidth of 16 GHz. This may be due to manufacturing tolerances, and also potentially due to the coupling between the W103-F monopole's housing and the connection to the 3743A extension head, which was not considered in simulation. Nevertheless, our measurement is in reasonable agreement with simulation, and the experimental confirmation of resonance at a high frequency shows the possibility of the extension to the upper mm-Wave frequency band. Fig. 2 (c) shows the simulated radiation patterns in the far-field of the tested silicon DRA. The azimuth and elevation planes correspond to the E-field and H-field planes, respectively. Both radiation patterns approximate the theoretical patterns of omnidirectional radiation [4]. Although the presence of minor undesired backlobes is noted, likely due to field interaction with the outer coaxial sleeve. A maximum gain of 2.6 dBi is given at the resonance frequency of 106.5 GHz with parabolic trajectories forming a symmetrical impact pattern around the vertical axis.

Fig. 2. (a) A photo of the proposed coaxial-W1-fed DRA, which was assembled by hand. Fig. 3. (b) Measured and simulated results of the reflection coefficient $|S_{11}|$ of the proposed DRA with $R = 710 \mu\text{m}$ excited by the coaxial W1-103F monopole. (c) Simulated radiation patterns in the E-plane (azimuth) in red color and H-plane (elevation) in blue color at the resonant frequency of 106.5 GHz.

4. NEAR-FIELD PROBE SCANNING FOR TESTING ANTENNAS

We demonstrate planar near-field (NF) probing using the proposed DRA for antenna testing. Planar near-field antenna measurements are preferable when far-field (FF) distances become impractical as frequency increases. This is because electrically-large, high-gain antennas such as Cassegrain dishes are increasingly necessary at higher frequencies, demanding a far-field distance that is problematic for high-frequency cabling and the management of frequency extension heads. For instance, we estimate that an ideal 30-dB circular aperture demands an $>7\text{m}$ standoff distance, and for 40 dB, this increases to $>70 \text{m}$. Ranging experiments at this distance are clearly impractical in a lab testing setting, leading us to seek alternative approaches. Following the needs for in-door antenna measurements, omnidirectional probes are therefore essential tools to evaluate radiation patterns of any complex antenna structure.

For this proof-of-concept demonstration, the antenna under test (AUT) is a 10-dB pyramidal horn antenna covering the range of 75-110 GHz. Planar scanning is performed using a XY plane with dimensions $11\lambda \times 11\lambda$ with a uniform sampling scheme of $\lambda/8$ sampling step. The DRA probe antenna is separated by a distance of 4λ from the AUT. The test probe is scanned across the chosen planar surface and the AUT is held stationary. The NF scan was performed using the same Anritsu MS4647B VNA and extension heads shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. A photo of the experimental setup for planar near-field scanning at the sample frequency of 107 GHz.

Figs. 4 (a) and (b) show the electric NF magnitude and phase, respectively. It can be seen that the field amplitude is localized in the center of the horn’s aperture, with slight convex curvature evident in the phase, as anticipated. There are also minor asymmetries noted, which are potentially due to undesired reflections, and can be removed with time-gating or additional absorbers in the setup. Thereafter, the FF radiation pattern can be recovered via a NF-FF transformation based on scalar diffraction theory, or Huygens’ principle [25]. The derived results are shown in Fig. 5. The 3-dB beamwidth of the E-plane is close to 40° , which is close to that estimated from theoretical calculations based on horn dimensions and operating wavelength [26].

Fig. 4. Measured NF data of (a) amplitude and (b) phase of the E-field at the sample frequency of 107 GHz.

Fig. 5. The FF radiation patterns show the directivity in (a) polar coordinates and (b) in 3-dimensional view.

We wish to emphasize the generality of this NF-FF transformation as, whilst conventional FF measurements are typically restricted to a single plane (i.e. E- or H-plane), our technique is capable of reconstructing the entire 3D half-space beyond the scanned aperture, including both near- and far-field regions of the AUT.

5. CONCLUSION

We have proposed and experimentally tested a coaxial-fed DRA operating at high frequencies enabled by intrinsic structural simplicity that is amenable to miniaturization. The DR is situated centrally on a vertical W1 monopole feed assembled by hand, providing one of the simplest and most precise micro-scale alignment concepts available. The silicon DR structure fabricated by DRIE, which is a high-precision and cost-effective process. We have achieved good matching at a resonance frequency above 100 GHz owing to the excitation of the TM_{016} mode. Simulated radiation patterns in far-field demonstrate omnidirectional radiation. Nevertheless, the DRA bandwidth is limited to 4 GHz, which corresponds to 25% of the simulation bandwidth due to possible fabrication tolerances. Demonstration of near-field probe scanning confirms the capabilities of the proposed DRA for future 6G antenna systems performance validation, without the need for impractically large transmission distances to characterize far-field patterns. The resulting FF directivity of the AUT is also presented after using the NF-FF transformation based on Huygens' principle. Future work includes enhancement of bandwidth via further exploitation of the degrees of design-freedom available and elimination of the undesired downward lobe effect via a conical reflective collar. This compact DRA omnidirectional antenna can potentially serve as a cost-effective, versatile probe antenna for the development and testing of 6G communication systems.

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